

IMPROVING THE FUNCTIONAL FITNESS OF RUNNERS OVER 400 METER

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Abstract: This article talks about improving the functional and technical preparation of 400 meter sprinters, analyzing running technique and rhythm during training.

Key words: 400-meter hurdlers, running technique, deceleration, shaking at the start, support reaction, obstacle, training.

INTRODUCTION

On November 5, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan - on the program for the development of the activities of sports and educational institutions until 2025 and - on the 2024 XXXIII Summer Olympics in Paris (France) and the XVII Decisions on the comprehensive preparation of Uzbek athletes for the Paralympic Games, to continue the efforts in the field more intensively, to determine the prospects for the development of sports and educational institutions, to prepare our athletes for the XXXIII Summer Olympic and XVII Paralympic Games in all aspects will be an important legal basis for ensuring readiness and successful participation. —According to the decision on the program for the development of the activities of sports-educational institutions until 2025, the program for the development of the activities of sports-educational institutions until 2025, —Roadmap for the implementation of the program in 2021-2022, the target indicators of the program and the main parameters of the

construction, reconstruction, perfect repair and equipment of Olympic and Paralympic reserve college facilities in 2022-2025 were approved.

The difficulty in running technique is to correctly determine the place of landing in front of the obstacle, because it is impossible to run such a long distance with a certain number of steps. The most qualified athletes approach the obstacle without changing the rhythm of steps and running speed. The diver must be able to aim with his eyes in order to place his foot at a certain distance from the hole.

This is perfected during training and competitions. In this case, it is very important to be able to pass through the deysin hole equally on both legs. The last step before depressing is somewhat shorter than the previous steps. The foot should be placed on the ground starting from the outer edge at a distance of 140-180 cm from the fence. Shortening the last step (for which the foot is placed closer to the projection of the UOM of the body) reduces the braking effect of the support reaction force during the front stance. During the squat, the runner's body leans slightly forward, and the bent leg is quickly brought forward by the knee. To maintain balance, the arm is extended forward or downward from the other side of the swinging leg.

Today, the sharp increase in sports results in international sports arenas requires the development of improved sports training methods. It is no secret to anyone that running technique and running rhythm directly depends on the result of the sport in the 400-meter distance race. Because an athlete with a high sports technique will definitely perform an economical movement with a beautiful run, which will ensure the improvement of the sports result. Taking into account these circumstances, when we analyze the running technique and rhythm of runners over 400 meters during training, it is known that most young athletes do not pay attention to being able to attack on both legs from the first day of training. It was determined during the observations that it would not grow until the end of the term and would cause difficulties in training later.

Therefore, teaching the technique of running over 400 meters and the rhythm between the jumps and the number of steps during training will improve the sports results. This shows that the selected topic is one of the actual topics in sports practice. Formation and development of jumping as a sport, although the first information about jumping over various obstacles was mentioned before 1873, it begins in the second half of the 19th century. According to the English historian F. Bebster, at the same time, the teachers of Eton College began to test their strength in running over holes. According to his contemporaries, such an emotional and artistic sport of running could not attract even younger sports enthusiasts. —Belta Life magazine featured an article about two sports enthusiasts competing to run over 10 equally spaced holes 3 feet 6 inches (106.7 cm) high. left. The magazine was published in 1853. This date is considered the beginning of the history of the development of cross-country skiing. The first indicator, which can be called the beginning of record results, was recorded in Great Britain in 1864 during a meeting of Cambridge and Oxford university students. The winner's time of 120 yards was 17.6 seconds. In the first rules for running over the pits with a height of 3 feet and 6 inches (1864) used for sheep pens, this height was mentioned as mandatory. Holes 10 yards apart made a competition distance of 120 yards. These dimensions have been preserved until our days

Women, older and younger girls and girls 30, 40, 60, 80 m, younger teenagers and boys 30, 40 and 80 m, men and older teenagers 35, 55 , 110, 200, 400 m. In addition, juniors can also run 110 m hurdles. The running distance over the pits is divided into the following phases:

- Acceleration after start and after start,
- going through depressions and holes,
- run between holes to reach the finish line

The low start in the horse race is more difficult than in the flat race, because the horse has to increase the speed as much as possible in the short distance to the

first hurdle, and it is necessary for the foot to meet the landing. It is necessary to take a certain amount of steps. Runners place the starting poles sometimes closer to the starting line, sometimes sliding, and sometimes further away from the starting line.

"Attention!" after the command, the gov osha raises his bowl a little higher than his shoulder.

In the first meters of running, the body should be recovered faster than the athlete, because in order to be better at crossing the first hurdle, he should start running in an almost normal position 9-10 meters after the start.

The distance to the first hole is covered in 7 or 8 steps. When there are 7 steps, at the start, the shaking (the first one that passes over the hole) leg is in front, and when there are 8, the breaking (when increasing the hole) leg is placed on the front post. To increase the hole (the step before hitting the hole is 25-30 cm shorter than the previous ones. This allows better kicking and passing obstacles easily. The starting point is at a distance of 195-220 cm from the hole. if 8 steps are taken in the distance from the line to the first hole, the length of the steps is approximately 55-115-130-145-160-180-205-175 cm. and the length of the steps is approximately 90-120-160-180-205-215-187 cm and is considered to be 215 cm from the hole.

CONCLUSION

In order to master the technique of running through high holes (106.7 cm), the height of the runner, in addition to other characteristics, is of great importance. If you are tall, it is possible to approach the technique of squatting to the technique of flat running. When the short-sized bulls cannot "step" over the barrier, their unsupported phase is prolonged and the speed of running between the bulls decreases.

The pedagogical research conducted on the analysis of the rhythm and technique of the 400 m distance runners made it possible to note the following conclusions:

1. In the conducted research, it was found out in the process of analysis that there is no scientific methodical literature on the study of running rhythm and technique of runners over 400 m;

2. In the conducted study, it was observed that the result of physical fitness and development of participants is important in the process of teaching running technique and rhythm of steps to runners over 400 m. 3. According to the results of the research, if attention is paid to training the ability to attack in both steps and pass the hole from the first day of the training of runners over 400 m in the running technique, then the athletes will master the technique of this type well later. and at the same time can improve sports performance.

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boshqarish texnologiyasi. Pedagogik mahorat. Ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal 3-son (2021-yil, iyun).